

Big Data to Enable Global Disruption of the Grapevine-powered Industries

D5.1 - Interactive Visualisation Components

DELIVERABLE NUMBER	D5.1
DELIVERABLE TITLE	Interactive Visualisation Components
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GRANT AGREEMENT N.	780751
PROJECT ACRONYM	BigDataGrapes
PROJECT FULL NAME	Big Data to Enable Global Disruption of the Grapevine-powered industries
STARTING DATE (DUR.)	01/01/2018 (36 months)
ENDING DATE	31/12/2020
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WORKPACKAGE N. TITLE	WP5 Leveraging Data Value
WORKPACKAGE LEADER	KU Leuven
DELIVERABLE N. TITLE	D5.1 Interactive Visualisation Components
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DOCUMENT URL	http://www.bigdatagrapes.eu/
DATE OF DELIVERY (CONTRACTUAL)	30 September 2018 (M9), 30 September 2019 (21)
DATE OF DELIVERY (SUBMITTED)	28 September 2018 (M9), 30 October (M22, Revised Version), 03 December 2019 (24)
VERSION STATUS	2.0 Final
NATURE	DEM (Demonstrator)
DISSEMINATION LEVEL	PU (Public)
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VERSION	MODIFICATION(S)	DATE	AUTHOR(S)
0.1	Initial ToC and document structure	15/08/2018	Nyi-Nyi Htun (KU Leuven)
0.2	Visualisation components	22/08/2018	Francisco Gutierrez (KU Leuven)
0.3	First draft	27/08/2018	Nyi-Nyi Htun (KU Leuven), Francisco Gutierrez (KU Leuven)
0.3.1	Edits and updates to all chapters	10/09/2018	Katrien Verbert (KU Leuven)
0.4	Second draft	11/09/2018	Nyi-Nyi Htun (KU Leuven)
0.4.1	Edits and updates to all chapters	13/09/2018	Katrien Verbert (KU Leuven)
0.5	Third draft	14/09/2018	Nyi-Nyi Htun (KU Leuven)
0.6	Internal Review	16/09/2018	Pythagoras Karampiperis (Agroknow)
1.0	Final edits after internal review	28/09/2018	Nyi-Nyi Htun (KU Leuven)
1.1	Revised version of v1 (with EC reviewers' comments)	30/10/2019	Nyi-Nyi Htun (KU Leuven)
1.3	Final draft of the updates	18/11/2019	Nyi-Nyi Htun (KU Leuven), Francisco Gutierrez (KU Leuven) Katrien Verbert (KU Leuven) Diego Rojo (KU Leuven)
1.5	Internal review	19/11/2019	Panagis Katsivelis (Agroknow)
2.0	Final edits after internal review	03/12/2019	Nyi-Nyi Htun (KU Leuven) Katrien Verbert (KU Leuven)

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ACRONYMS LIST

PA	Precision agriculture
WP	Work package
NDVI	Normalized difference vegetation index
API	Application programming interface
HTML	Hypertext markup language
CSV	Comma-Separated Values

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 5.1 of work package 5 is to develop interactive visualisation components in order to leverage interpretation and understanding of complex data. As a starting point, a systematic review¹ was conducted where we thoroughly analysed a total of 140 research papers and found various decision support systems and visualisation tools that have been proposed in the domain of agriculture. Based on the findings of this review, we developed a total of six interactive visualisation components and delivered in the first version² of deliverable 5.1. In this second version of the deliverable, we have added new visualisations and also improved the existing ones. We have also updated the development technology including the framework and libraries to be in line with the expertise of the development teams at the partner institutions.

This document is structured as follows. Section 1 provides an introduction to the deliverable describing the existing work, previous deliverable and motivations. In section 2, the new platform, including individual components, is described in detail together with the development technology. In section 3, a user manual with detailed instructions on how to obtain the code and deploy the platform is provided. This document concludes with section 4 where a summary of the deliverable is underlined.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2019.05.053>

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1481788>

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1. INTRODUCTION

The volume of data available from farms has rapidly increased as the use of farm sensors, high-tech harvesters and drones is becoming more popular. Many farmers, therefore, feel overloaded by this large volume of data, and need additional tools for understanding and interpreting their data³. Visualisation is a powerful technique to mitigate these issues and has demonstrated its usefulness in the precision agriculture (PA) domain⁴. Visualisation is also effective at communicating uncertainty in seasonal climate prediction⁵, an important task in agriculture. As Rind et al.⁶ stated, visualisation provides a way to utilise “the processing power of modern computers with human cognition and visual abilities to better support analysis tasks”.

The benefits of visualising complex data arise from being able to better interact and understand data by aggregating, filtering, searching or scaling down relevant information. As such, a large volume of data with potentially complex information becomes more easily consumable. Due to such benefits, visualisation tools have been widely used in various domains to assist with tasks that might otherwise require significant cognitive effort. For instance, analysis of past volcanic activities using a time series graph can uncover trends and can aid in predicting future eruption of a volcano. In the domain of agriculture, visualisation tools are being used in a number of sub-areas, including viticulture, dairy farming, wheat production, pest management, crop management, irrigation management and fertiliser management.

Under the work package 5 (WP5: leveraging data value), BigDataGrapes will develop a number of visualisation components and a trust-aware decision support system for stakeholders in the grapevine-powered industry. As a first step towards accomplishing this, we conducted a systematic review gathering an exhaustive list of decision support systems and visualisation tools that have been proposed in the domain of agriculture. We reviewed a total of 140 research papers thoroughly and presented our findings from 61 relevant papers. Results of this review have been disseminated in the *Journal of Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*⁷.

We found that the majority of the decision support systems in agriculture use at least one interactive visualisation technique which includes: 2D geographical maps, heatmaps (layered over 2D maps), time series, histograms, bar charts, pie charts, radar charts, dashboards and cross section representations of a farm. Thus, various visualisation techniques are being used in different areas of agriculture. Nevertheless, we discovered that the area of agricultural decision support systems still lacks the support from interactive visualisations with modern technology and uncertainty visualisations. For instance, the majority of the interfaces were designed for standalone PCs which lacks the flexibility and cross-platform support unlike web applications. Taking into account these findings, we designed a total of six most widely used visualisations to

³ Ruß, G., Kruse, R., Schneider, M. and Wagner, P., 2009. Visualization of agriculture data using self-organizing maps. In *Applications and Innovations in Intelligent Systems XVI* (pp. 47-60). Springer, London.

⁴ Wachowiak, M.P., Walters, D.F., Kovacs, J.M., Wachowiak-Smolikova, R. and James, A.L., 2017. Visual analytics and remote sensing imagery to support community-based research for precision agriculture in emerging areas. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 143, pp.149-164.

⁵ Frías, M.D., Iturbide, M., Manzanas, R., Bedia, J., Fernández, J., Herrera, S., Cofiño, A.S. and Gutiérrez, J.M., 2018. An R package to visualize and communicate uncertainty in seasonal climate prediction. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 99, pp.101-110.

⁶ Rind, A., Wang, T.D., Aigner, W., Miksch, S., Wongsuphasawat, K., Plaisant, C. and Shneiderman, B., 2013. Interactive information visualization to explore and query electronic health records. *Foundations and Trends® in Human-Computer Interaction*, 5(3), pp.207-298.

⁷ Gutiérrez, F., Htun, N.N., Schlenz, F., Kasimati, A. and Verbert, K., 2019. A review of visualisations in agricultural decision support systems: An HCI perspective. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 163, p.104844.

showcase in the first version⁸ of deliverable 5.1; these visualisations were: 2D map with a heatmap layer, time series, histogram, bar chart, radar chart and scatter plot (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Six visualisation components that were showcased in the first version of deliverable 5.1

The aim of this deliverable is to provide users with flexible, reusable, responsive and interactive visualisation components. In its current version, we have extended the list by adding new visualisation components and also updated the existing ones. The new visualisation components are: pie chart, parallel coordinates, data table and progress circle (see Section 2.1.2). We have also extended the use of visualisation libraries from Chart.js to Uber’s react-vis and Vega-Lite, together these libraries provide comprehensive visualisation abilities and complement one another (see Section 0). To develop web components, we used the Polymer library⁹ in the previous version. In this version, however, we have migrated from Polymer to React¹⁰, because we discovered that the development teams at many of the pilot partner institutions are more familiar with React than Polymer.

Over the past months, we have also discovered that the available data and the structure of data between the pilot partners are quite heterogeneous. Yet, the partners should still be able to explore their datasets by means of visualisations and make sense of the data at hand. To overcome this challenge, in this version of deliverable 5.1, we have designed a data exploration platform that can accommodate heterogeneous datasets (see Section 2.1 for details). Using this platform, users can flexibly summon the visualisation components regardless of the varying structures of the datasets.

In section 2, detailed descriptions of the new platform, visualisation components and development technologies are presented. A user manual has also been provided in section 3 describing detailed instructions on how to utilise the tool.

⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1481788>

⁹ <https://www.polymer-project.org/>

¹⁰ <https://reactjs.org/>

2. PLATFORM AND DEVELOPMENT TECHNOLOGY

2.1. PLATFORM

Exploring large, unorganised, and heterogeneous datasets can be a challenging task. To overcome this, we have designed a data exploration platform that can accommodate various forms of data. This platform enables project partners to import any type of data and select visualisation components. By doing so, users can flexibly summon the visualisation components regardless of the varying structures of the datasets. Information visualisation techniques can support data examination by visually identifying trends, anomalies, and support in the understanding of large, complex data structures. We designed Vex, a simple-yet-powerful reactive Web Application that incorporates a collection of reusable and simple to use data visualisation components.

Vex (v0.1) is designed to be easy to use, to handle large amounts of data, and to enable visual and interactive exploration of data. Vex allows interaction inside each of the visualisation components to filter and sort information. Interactivity between components will be included in a future update. The system allows users to customise each of the components with personalised colours, filtering and basic operations (sum, median, mean, min, max). Multiple visualisation components can be added allowing comparisons for further exploration of the data.

In the latest version of Vex, the library consists of the following visualisation components: bar chart and histogram, time series, scatterplot, radar chart, pie chart, choropleth map, parallel coordinates, data table and progress circle. Components will be continuously added in future version updates. In the following subsections, we describe the system in more detail.

2.1.1. Overview

Figure 2 shows an overview of the platform where we can see 3 distinct areas: *data selector*, *visualisation selector* and *visualisation area*. The *data selector* area allows the user to select a dataset to visualise. The platform currently supports files in a Comma-Separated Values (CSV) format. The CSV format is one of the most broadly used forms to transfer and organise data; we mainly focused on CSV for now because it is also the most commonly used format among the pilot partners. The platform can read any standard CSV file; this file must include a header for each column. Row numbers (if any) are recognised and included as a separate column. In Figure 2, we can see that the climatic dataset¹¹ (climate.csv), authored by INRA, has been selected. The *visualisation selector* allows the user to select the type(s) of visualisation she/he wishes to use. Here, the user may select as many types of visualisation as needed from the list. The *visualisation area* then displays the dataset based on the user's selections. In the next section, we describe each of the components in the visualisation area.

¹¹ https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1ZyX5LFiOLoI_qJKZiWoyt8oE5pailQSf?usp=sharing

Figure 2: Overview of the platform showing 3 distinct areas: data selector, visualisation selector and visualisation area.

2.1.2. Visualisation Components

In the previous version of deliverable 5.1, we showcased a total of 6 components that are among the most common visualisations in Agriculture; these are: time series, bar charts, histograms, scatter plots, radar charts and 2D heatmaps. In this version, we have extended the list by adding new visualisation components and also updated the existing ones. As stated in the Introduction section, we have also migrated from Polymer to the more popular React framework and extended the Chart.js library with Uber’s react-vis and Vega-Lite libraries; details are presented in Section 0.

In addition, the interaction capabilities of the components have been further elaborated to enable users to interactively explore a visualisation and to customise the representation. In the following, we describe the interaction capabilities according to the taxonomy of interaction types that has been presented by Yi et al¹²:

Select interaction techniques enable users to mark data items of interest. The technique is used to select items that may be interesting to revisit at a later stage.

Explore interaction techniques enable users to examine a different subset of the data. A typical explore operation is *panning* that enables users to see a different part of a geographic map.

Reconfigure interaction techniques enable users to change the arrangement of representations to provide them with different perspectives onto the data set. Reconfigure interaction techniques

¹² Yi, J.S., ah Kang, Y. and Stasko, J., 2007. Toward a deeper understanding of the role of interaction in information visualization. IEEE transactions on visualization and computer graphics, 13(6), pp.1224-1231.

allow users to change the way data items are arranged in order to provide different perspectives on the data set. Examples include the selection of different data elements to represent in parallel coordinates or changing the attributes assigned to the x- and y-axis of scatter plots.

Encode interaction techniques enable users to alter the representation of data, such as changing a pie chart to a histogram. As with other interaction techniques, the purpose of changing the type of representation is to uncover new aspects or patterns. In addition to changing the visualisation techniques, some tools also allow users to change the colour scheme or size.

Abstract / elaborate interaction techniques allow users to adjust the level of abstraction of a data representation. A *tool-tip* interaction technique that provides the user with additional information belongs to this category. Another common abstract/elaborate technique is *zooming*. Through zooming, users can change the scale of a representation so that they can see an overview of a larger data set (using zoom-out) or the detailed view of a smaller data set (using zoom-in).

Filter interaction techniques allow users to change the set of data items based on some specific conditions. In this type of interaction, users specify a range or condition, so that only data items meeting those criteria are presented. Sliders are for instance commonly used to filter the time period that is of interest. Users select ranges by moving sliders to show the data items that meet particular constraints. Many other systems provide a check or input box that enables users to filter the data items.

Connect interaction techniques are used to “(1) highlight associations and relationships between data items that are already represented and (2) show hidden data items that are relevant to a specified item”. A typical example is a *brushing* technique that highlights a data element that is selected in one view in other related views.

2.1.2.1. Bar Chart & Histogram

A bar chart shows comparisons among discrete categories. One axis of the chart shows the specific categories being compared, and the other axis represents a measured value. Bar charts present bars clustered in groups of more than one, showing the values of more than one measured variable. A histogram is a type of bar chart typically used to represent the distribution of data points in a dataset. Thus, a single component is used to visualise bar chart and histogram. The user can choose to see the distribution of data points by aggregating the columns using the setup page (Figure 3). The following interaction capabilities have been added to the component.

- **Reconfigure:** In this new version, users can select columns from the data set and select a function to aggregate the data; for example. In Figure 3, user can select a column “Fruity” from the dataset and aggregate the value using the mean function. This column will then be added to the bar chart if the checkbox is selected.
- **Encode:** The bar chart can be further customised by selecting a colour for the new calculated value.
- **Abstract/elaborate:** The visualisation shows tooltips on top of the bars when the user hovers the mouse over each of the bars in the graph.

Figure 3: Bar chart and histogram

Reusing the Component

The following example code shows how the component can be imported and configured in the React framework.

```
import React, { Component } from 'react';
import './VizComponents/Components.css';
import Barchart from './VizComponents/Barchart/Barchart.js';

export class App extends Component {

  constructor(props) {
    super(props);
    this.state = {
      Dataset: /** CSV File */,
      Columns: ["column 1", "column 2", ... ],
    };
  }

  render() {
    return(<Barchart title="Bar Chart" data = {this.state.Dataset} columns = {this.state.Columns} />);
  }
}
```

2.1.2.2. Time Series

A time series is a distribution of data points visualised in time order. It is usually presented as a sequence with successive equally spaced points in time. Figure 4 shows the new version of the time series component. The following interaction capabilities have been added to the component:

- **Encode:** The setup page allows users to customise the colour of data series.
- **Reconfigure:** In the setup page, the user can select the fields to display. Then assign a colour to the data selection. For example in Figure 4, the user selected the column “Dat-vrz” and assigns a colour. The checkbox indicates that the selection is active and visible in the time series visualisation.
- **Abstract/elaborate:** The visualisation shows tooltips when the user hovers the mouse over the data points in the graph. A zooming option is available when there are too many data points in the visual component.

Figure 4: Time series

Reusing the Component

The following example code shows how the component can be imported and configured in the React framework.

```
import React, { Component } from 'react';
import './VizComponents/Components.css';
import Timeseries from './VizComponents/Timeseries/Timeseries.js';

export class App extends Component {

  constructor(props) {
    super(props);
    this.state = {
      Dataset: /** CSV File */,
      Columns: ["column 1", "column 2", ... ],
    };
  }

  render() {
    return(<Timeseries title="Time series" data = {this.state.Dataset} columns = {this.state.Columns} />);
  }
}
```

```
}  
}
```

2.1.2.3. Scatterplot

A scatter plot is a two-dimensional visualisation that uses dots to represent the values obtained for two different variables - one plotted along the x-axis and the other plotted along the y-axis. The new version of a scatterplot visualisation can be seen in Figure 5. The following interaction capabilities have been added to the component:

- **Encode:** The setup page allows users to customise the colour of each x and y axes pair.
- **Reconfigure:** In the setup page, the user can select the data to display, more fields can be added by clicking the “add field” option, datasets can be enabled or disabled by clicking the checkboxes. For example, in Figure 5, the user selected the columns “MTC” and “SSM” from the dataset and assigns a colour. The checkbox indicates that the selection is active and visible in the scatterplot visualisation.
- **Abstract/elaborate:** The visualisation shows tooltips when the user hovers the mouse over the data points in the graph. A zooming option is available when there are too many data points in the visual component.

Figure 5: Scatterplot

Reusing the Component

The following example code shows how the component can be imported and configured in the React framework.

```
import React, { Component } from 'react';  
import './VizComponents/Components.css';  
import Scatterplot from './VizComponents/Scatterplot/Scatterplot.js';  
  
export class App extends Component {  
  
  constructor(props) {  
    super(props);  
    this.state = {  
      Dataset: /** CSV File **/,  

```

```

    Columns: ["column 1", "column 2", ... ],
  };
}

render() {
return(<Scatterplot title="Scatter Plot" data = {this.state.Dataset} columns = {this.state.Columns}
/>);
}
}
}

```

2.1.2.4. Radar chart

A radar chart is a representation of multivariate data in the form of a two-dimensional chart of three or more quantitative variables represented on axes starting from the same point. Figure 6 shows the radar chart component in the new version. The following interaction capabilities have been added to the component:

- **Encode:** The setup page allows users to customise the colour of each axis.
- **Reconfigure:** In the setup page, the user can select the data to display, more fields can be added by clicking the “add field” option, datasets can be enabled or disabled by clicking the checkboxes. For example in Figure 6, the user selected the columns “Fruity”, “Acid”, “Fat” and “Candy” from the dataset and assigns a colour. The checkbox indicates that the selection is active and visible in the radar chart visualisation.
- **Abstract/elaborate:** The visualisation shows tooltips when the user hovers the mouse over the data points in the graph.

Figure 6: Radar chart

Reusing the Component

The following example code shows how the component can be imported and configured in the React framework.

```

import React, { Component } from 'react';
import './VizComponents/Components.css';
import Radarchart from './VizComponents/Radarchart/Radarchart.js';

```

```

export class App extends Component {

  constructor(props) {
    super(props);
    this.state = {
      Dataset: /** CSV File */,
      Columns: ["column 1", "column 2", ... ],
    };
  }

  render() {
    return(<Radarchart title="Radar Chart" data = {this.state.Dataset} columns = {this.state.Columns} />);
  }
}

```

2.1.2.5. Pie chart

A pie chart represents the proportion of a quality using slices in a circular pie. The arc length of each slice is proportional to the quantity it represents. Pie chart is a new addition in this version of the deliverable. The following interaction capabilities have been added to the component:

- **Encode:** The setup page allows users to customise the colour of each slice.
- **Reconfigure:** In the setup page, the user can select the data to display, more fields can be added by clicking the “add field” option, datasets can be enabled or disabled by clicking the checkboxes. For example in Figure 7, the user selected the columns “Fruity”, “Acid” and “Candy” from the dataset and assigns a colour. The checkbox indicates that the selection is active and visible in the radar chart visualisation.
- **Abstract/elaborate:** The visualisation shows tooltips when the user hovers the mouse over the data points in the graph.

Figure 7: Pie chart

Reusing the Component

The following example code shows how the component can be imported and configured in the React framework.

```
import React, { Component } from 'react';
import './VizComponents/Components.css';
import Piechart from './VizComponents/Piechart/Piechart.js';

export class App extends Component {

  constructor(props) {
    super(props);
    this.state = {
      Dataset: /** CSV File */,
      Columns: ["column 1", "column 2", ... ],
    };
  }

  render() {
    return(<Piechart title="Pie Chart" data = {this.state.Dataset} columns = {this.state.Columns} />);
  }
}
```

2.1.2.6. Choropleth map

Choropleth maps are geographical representations of data where individual values contained in an area of interest are represented with a spectrum of colours. In agricultural visualisations, data such as normalised difference vegetation index (NDVI) is often shown as a layer of heatmap on top of a 2D geographical map. Figure 8 shows food incident records from 2017 to 2018 on a map component with colour scales. Choropleth maps are slightly different from heatmap in that they are often used to show data across larger geographical areas such as states and countries. The following interaction capabilities have been added to the component:

- **Reconfigure:** In the setup page, the user can select the data to display. For example, in Figure 8 the user selected the columns “Location”, and “Year-Month” from the dataset the colours are assigned automatically.
- **Abstract/elaborate:** The visualisation shows tooltips when the user hovers the mouse over the data points in the graph.
- **Filter:** Users can use the brushing technique to select and filter out data in visualisation.

Figure 8: Choropleth map

Reusing the Component

The following example code shows how the component can be imported and configured in the React framework.

```
import React, { Component } from 'react';
import './VizComponents/Components.css';
import Choropleth from './VizComponents/Choropleth/Choropleth.js';

export class App extends Component {

  constructor(props) {
    super(props);
    this.state = {
      Dataset: /** CSV File */,
      Columns: ["column 1", "column 2", ... ],
    };
  }

  render() {
    return(<Choropleth title="Choropleth Map" data = {this.state.Dataset} columns = {this.state.Columns} />);
  }
}
```

2.1.2.7. Parallel Coordinates

Parallel coordinates are used to visualise multidimensional data. Each column (parallel lines) represents a variable and can span up to n parallel lines (see Figure 9). Each horizontal line represents a set of data points across the parallel lines. Parallel coordinates are a new addition in this version of the deliverable. The following interaction capabilities have been implemented:

- **Reconfigure:** The setup page allows users to select the field to display in each parallel line.
- **Encode:** Users can select a category column; the colours are automatically set for the selection.
- **Filter:** Users can use the brushing technique to select and filter out data in the parallel coordinates' visualisation.

- **Explore:** A panning option is available when there are too many columns in the visualisation. Users can use the panning option to scroll from left to right, or from top to bottom, depending on the amount of information in the graph.

Figure 9: Parallel coordinates

Reusing the Component

The following example code shows how the component can be imported and configured in the React framework.

```
import React, { Component } from 'react';
import './VizComponents/Components.css';
import PCoordinates from './VizComponents/PCoordinates/PCoordinates.js';

export class App extends Component {

  constructor(props) {
    super(props);
    this.state = {
      Dataset: /** CSV File */,
      Columns: ["column 1", "column 2", ... ],
    };
  }

  render() {
    return(<PCoordinates title="Parallel Coordinates" data = {this.state.Dataset} columns =
    {this.state.Columns} />);
  }
}
```

2.1.2.8. Data Table

Data tables are useful to show the raw data in an organised manner (see Figure 10). Spreadsheets are the most familiar type of data tables. The data table component is also a new addition in this version of the deliverable. The following interaction capabilities have been implemented:

- **Reconfigure:** Users can click on the header of each column to sort the data by column.

- **Explore:** A scroll/pagination option is available when there are too many columns/rows in the data table, users can use the scroll option to scroll from left to right, or from top to bottom, depending on the amount of information in the table.

Figure 10: Data table

Reusing the Component

The following example code shows how the component can be imported and configured in the React framework.

```
import React, { Component } from 'react';
import './VizComponents/Components.css';
import Datatable from './VizComponents/Datatable/Datatable.js';

export class App extends Component {

  constructor(props) {
    super(props);
    this.state = {
      Dataset: /** CSV File */,
      Columns: ["column 1", "column 2", ... ],
    };
  }

  render() {
    return(<Datatable title="Data Table" data = {this.state.Dataset} columns = {this.state.Columns} />);
  }
}
```

2.1.2.9. Progress Circle

Progress circles show a circular progress bar typically indicating a distribution (like pie charts) or progress (see Figure 11). Progress circle is a new addition in this version of the deliverable. The following interaction capabilities have been implemented:

- **Reconfigure:** In the setup page, the user can select the data to display, more fields can be added by clicking the “add field” option, datasets can be enabled or disabled by clicking the checkboxes. For example in Figure 11 the user selected the columns “Fruity”, “Candy”, “Balanced” and “Acid” from the dataset, selects a function to apply, in this case the mean

function, and assigns a colour. The checkbox indicates that the selection is active and visible in the radar chart visualisation.

- **Encode:** The setup page allows users to customise the colour.

Figure 11: Progress circle

Reusing the Component

The following example code shows how the component can be imported and configured in the React framework.

```
import React, { Component } from 'react';
import './VizComponents/Components.css';
import ProgressCircle from './VizComponents/ProgressCircle/ProgressCircle.js';

export class App extends Component {

  constructor(props) {
    super(props);
    this.state = {
      Dataset: /** CSV File */,
      Columns: ["column 1", "column 2", ... ],
    };
  }

  render() {
    return(<ProgressCircle title="Progress Circle" data = {this.state.Dataset} columns =
    {this.state.Columns} />);
  }
}
```

2.2. DEVELOPMENT TECHNOLOGY

The technologies used in this version of deliverable are: Meteor, React, Vega-Lite, Chart.js and Uber's react-vis. Meteor is a full stack framework to build Web Applications in JavaScript. It integrates with MongoDB and uses a Distributed Data Protocol together with a publish-subscribe pattern to spread data changes from server to clients without requiring writing complex synchronization code.

React¹³ is a JavaScript library maintained by Facebook for building user interfaces and has recently become extremely popular. React can be used to build Web Applications; it is optimal for fetching reactive data in modern complex applications. In the previous version, we used the Polymer library¹⁴ to develop Web Components. Similar to React, Polymer was a JavaScript library for developing responsive web applications. However, over the past months, we learned that the development teams at many of the pilot partner institutions are more familiar with React than Polymer. The development team at Agroknow, for example, has already been using React for the FOODAKAI¹⁵ application. Therefore, we decided to migrate to React in this version.

We reused the Chart.js¹⁶ library from the previous version in order to rebuild some of the existing visualisation components. In addition to Chart.js, we also started using a number of other visualisation libraries in this version. These are Uber's react-vis¹⁷ and Vega-Lite¹⁸. Uber's react-vis is a JavaScript library that contains a collection of well-known visualisation components that are easy to implement and understand. Vega-Lite is a high-level grammar that enables the agile specification of data visualisations. Vega-Lite combines a traditional grammar of graphics, providing visual encoding rules and logic composition for a layered display of information, following a well-defined syntax of interaction. Both react-vis and Vega-Lite libraries offer a number of additional visualisations that compliment Chart.js.

¹³ <https://reactjs.org/>

¹⁴ <https://www.polymer-project.org/>

¹⁵ <https://www.agroknow.com/foodakai>

¹⁶ <https://www.chartjs.org/>

¹⁷ <https://uber.github.io/react-vis/>

¹⁸ <https://vega.github.io/vega-lite/>

3. USER MANUAL

3.1. DOWNLOADING THE CODE

The code for this version of deliverable 5.1 has been uploaded to the BigDataGrape github repository: <https://github.com/BigDataGrapes-EU/visualisationdemo>.

One can follow the following steps to download and utilise the tool.

1. Download meteor framework from <https://www.meteor.com/install>
2. Install the framework following the instructions provided.
3. Download or clone the project:

```
$ git clone https://github.com/BigDataGrapes-EU/visualisationcomponents.git
```

4. Navigate to the cloned/downloaded folder: `cd visualisationcomponents`

```
$ cd visualisationcomponents
```

5. Run the project using the meteor command, this will automatically install all the dependencies needed and run the project.

```
$ meteor
```

6. In case of missing dependencies simply run:

```
$ meteor npm install
```

7. Open the application in browser <http://localhost:3000/>

3.2. RUNNING THE APPLICATION

1. Open the application in browser <http://localhost:3000/>
2. Click on the Data Selector component.

3. Select a csv file

4. Once the data is loaded, select a Visualisation Component from the list:

5. For example, click bar chart. Then, a bar chart component will appear where it can be customised as follows:

6. After clicking the Ok button, the component will show the bar chart. The component can be edited, expanded to large size or closed using the settings located in the upper right corner.

climate.csv

2522 records - 0.5 Mb

open new file...

 Bar Chart		
 Radar Chart		
 P. Circle		
 HeatMap		
 VegaLiteDemo		

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this document, we presented a new version of deliverable 5.1: Interactive Visualisation Components, produced under work package 5. In the previous version, we showcased a total of six most used visualisations; these were: 2D map with a heatmap layer, time series, histogram, bar chart, radar chart and scatter plot (see Figure 1). In this version of the deliverable, we have extended the list by adding new visualisation components and also updated the existing ones. The new visualisation components are pie chart, parallel coordinates, data table and progress circle (see Section 2.1.2). In Section 0, we have explained in detail the new platform including the improvements made to the existing components, and the new ones.

We have also migrated from Polymer to React to be in line with the development teams of the pilot partners. Besides, we used additional visualisation libraries such as Uber's react-vis and Vega-Lite to show their capabilities and add the varieties. Detailed explanations of the development technology used, including the framework and libraries, have been presented in Section 0. All of the codes have been published at the Github repository of BigDataGrapes (<https://github.com/BigDataGrapes-EU/visualisationdemo>). A user manual with detailed steps on how to obtain the code and run the application has been provided in Section 3.